

8T – Interactions Separation & The Gravitational Class

O Manor

September 14, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the first term of the primordial coupling series, it is possible to construct the process of separation of the first three interactions. That is by using the fact that the primes composing the second and third interactions are matching the even variation term of the strong. Gravity is not part of the separation moment in the 8T thesis, as it is different in nature from the independent element.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea of separation of the forces, i.e. Bosonic net variations. We have previously mentioned that the direction of the arrow is the direction of time. The strongest interactions appear at the first, the result is an endless process of clustering, with weaker and weaker interactions, given by ratio of net to total.

$$\overrightarrow{1 > \frac{3}{30} > \frac{5}{128} > \frac{7}{850} \dots}$$

When the author derived the coupling series back in March 2021, each coupling term was analyzed by extracting the net variation element. In the following page, presented the original part of the construction of the pre-equation idea which yielded the primorial:

Analyze the (7,11) total variations pair with $N_V = (+1)$:

Total variations sum is divisible by two:

$$18/2 = 9$$

And then by three

$$9/3 = 3$$

We know that we have $N_V = (+1)$ so it can be extracted to yield:

$$F_1 = 8 + 1$$

However, even amounts of variations vanish so we can ignore the element 8 and write:

$$F_1 = 1$$

Notice that the first interaction can be represented the following way:

$$[W^- + \gamma + g] = 9 \tag{1.62}$$

That is because each Boson is isomorphic to a prime, that was speculated on theorem two, pre-equation idea:

$$W^- \equiv +3$$

$$\gamma \equiv +5$$

so already in the first term we can represent the Bosons of the rest of the two interactions. Since we have taken it out from the total sum, we have separated it from the mixture of the three interactions. The Boson of the weak interaction can be either one of the three. We have taken W^- as it has the same charge as the electron, fact that the author used for the SUSY construction. So now after the Gluon was taken out:

$$[W^- + \gamma + g] \rightarrow [W^- + \gamma] + g$$

Next, the term in the parenthesis represents the Electroweak Bosonic combinations. This term create total sum of an even, and thus we took it to zero in the 8T thesis. However here we have two independent Bosons, so each can be set in his way. After the Gluon was separated, the electroweak combination is needed to be separated, to the electric Boson, the photon and the weak interaction Bosons. The combination of all the three also implies higher state of energy and as each interaction stands on its own, the energy is lower. So already we can reason why the forces should be separated.

$$[W^- + \gamma + g] \rightarrow E_n + E_{n+1} + E_{n+2} = E_{3n+3}$$

$$E_{3n+3} > E_n \cap E_{n+1} \cap E_{n+2}$$

That is to state that the SEW combined term has a higher energy state and each of the Bosons in itself, which indicate nature aspires to "break the combination" of the SEW into separated elements. It is quite a remarkable fact that the Bosons of the first three interactions sum exactly to the term of the first interaction to equation (1.62). Therefore, the 8T predicts that first the strong is separated than the Electroweak combined term. In contrast to other theories that aspire to describe Gravity moment of separation, the 8T does not include Gravity directly, as it is a composite interaction that has infinite variations, assuming we use the spin representation of the main equation.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4}$$

$$N_{VK3} \not\equiv N_{VK4}$$

The structure of the gravity is invariant to the change of the element. Since the total spin is invariant, i.e. two, there is not a change in the nature of gravity; the structure is the same while the composite element could be different.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

the last interesting twist, the fact that the three terms are combined in one equation without Gravity, is already means that Gravity has broken, as the term (1.62) contains three distinct amount of net curvature, put another way, those interactions are just different amounts of gravity, manifested in different primes. So the term already contain the separation of "gravity" if the author reasoned clearly enough. To put this confusing idea another way, **Gravity is the class and the interactions are different objects in the class**, so the fact that we have different objects in the class means that the class it is not unified, i.e. that the class is separated or "broken". (1.62) indicate that these are the interactions that were separated as they exactly match the Bosons of two next interactions. To express the idea of the Gravity class we can define a set of net variations:

$$\Lambda: Top \rightarrow Set$$

$$G_{class} = \{N_V | N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1)\} \tag{1.63}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad